

Number of Normal Subgroups of a Finite Group

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By

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DECLARATION

I, **Monis Iqbal**, Roll Number: **220466**, hereby declare that the internship report/project titled "**Number of Normal Subgroups of a Finite Group**", submitted to the **Department of Mathematics, Amar Singh College**, is an original work completed by me under the guidance of **Dr. Sajad Hussain Ahanger and Firdous Ahmad Mala**.

I declare that this work is the result of my own independent effort, and I have acknowledged all sources (books, articles, essays, theses, online sources). No material other than the listed references has been used in this work.

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This is to certify that the internship report/project titled "Number of Normal Subgroups of a Finite Group" submitted by **Monis Iqbal Ganie**, Roll Number: **220466**, of the **Department of Mathematics, Amar Singh College, Cluster University Srinagar**, is a bonafide record of work carried out during the Internship/Research Internship Programme, under my supervision and guidance.

This report has been submitted as a partial fulfillment of the requirements for the completion of the Internship/Research Internship Programme for the **5th Semester (02 Credit Course; 60 Hours)**, as per the guidelines of the **National Education Policy (NEP), 2020**.

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Abstract

The goal of this research is to determine the number of normal subgroups of a finite group, focusing on their role in group structure and classification. In this study, we will identify the patterns in normal subgroups, their distribution, and the factors influencing their count. We will explore different methods for determining normality, such as conjugacy classes, Sylow theorems, and automorphisms. Additionally, we examine various classes of groups, including cyclic groups, symmetric groups, and p -groups. This study concludes that the number of normal subgroups is closely related to the structural properties of a group.

1 Introduction

Normal subgroups play a crucial role in group theory. It serves as the foundation for quotient groups. Counting normal subgroups in finite groups is not only a theoretical challenge but also an essential step in understanding group classification and structure. The aim of this research is to investigate the number of normal subgroups of a finite group. It focuses on methods for identifying and counting normal subgroups. It gives special attention to different group classes including cyclic groups, symmetric groups, P -groups. In this paper, we will also examine the role of Sylow theorems in determining normal subgroups and their connection to larger group structures. By investigating these aspects, this work aims to provide a deeper understanding of normal subgroups in finite groups.

2 History of Normality in Groups

The concept of normal subgroups has a deep-rooted history in the development of group theory, tracing back to the foundational work of 19th-century mathematicians. The origins of normal subgroups are closely tied to early studies of permutation groups and solvability, particularly in the work of Évariste Galois.

2.1 Galois and the Birth of Group Theory (1830s)

Evariste Galois introduced the idea of groups in his work on polynomial equations. While he did not explicitly define normal subgroups, his analysis of permutations and the conditions for the solvability of polynomials led to what would later be recognized as normality. Galois observed that certain subgroups of permutation groups remained unchanged under conjugation, laying the foundation for the modern concept of normal subgroups.

2.2 Jordan, Cauchy, and Early Group Theory (Late 19th Century)

Camille Jordan and Augustin Cauchy expanded on Galois' ideas, formalizing group theory and introducing deeper structural insights. Jordan's work on substitution groups (permutation groups) in the 1870s explicitly considered subgroups that remained invariant under conjugation, effectively formalizing the notion of normal subgroups.

2.3 Sylow's Theorems and Normality (1872)

Ludvig Sylow's theorems, published in 1872, provided key results on the existence and uniqueness of p -subgroups in finite groups. While the Sylow theorems do not directly define normal subgroups, they establish conditions under which a Sylow p -subgroup is normal, further advancing the study of subgroup structure.

2.4 Modern Group Theory and Normal Subgroups (20th Century Onward)

With the formalization of abstract group theory in the early 20th century by mathematicians such as Emmy Noether and Issai Schur, normal subgroups became a fundamental concept in algebra. The introduction of quotient groups and the development of the isomorphism theorems cemented normal subgroups as a critical tool for understanding group structures.

In contemporary mathematics, normal subgroups play a crucial role in various areas, including the classification of finite simple groups, algebraic topology, and representation theory. Their significance extends beyond pure mathematics, influencing fields such as cryptography, coding theory, and physics.

3 Groups

3.1 Definition

A group is a set G equipped with a binary operation (\cdot) that satisfies the following axioms [1]:

- **Closure:** For all $a, b \in G$, we have $a \cdot b \in G$.
- **Associativity:** For all $a, b, c \in G$,

$$(a \cdot b) \cdot c = a \cdot (b \cdot c).$$

- **Identity Element:** There exists an element $e \in G$ such that for all $a \in G$,

$$a \cdot e = e \cdot a = a.$$

- **Inverse Element:** For each $a \in G$, there exists an element $a^{-1} \in G$ such that

$$a \cdot a^{-1} = a^{-1} \cdot a = e.$$

3.2 Examples

Examples [2]:

- The set of integers \mathbb{Z} under addition.
- The set of nonzero real numbers \mathbb{R}^* under multiplication.
- The symmetric group S_n : The set of all permutations of n elements under composition.

4 Subgroups

Definition: A subgroup H of a group G is a subset of G that is itself a group under the operation of G [1].

4.1 Subgroup Criteria [2]

A subset $H \subseteq G$ is a subgroup if it satisfies the following conditions:

- **Closure:** For all $a, b \in H$, we have $a \cdot b \in H$.
- **Identity:** The identity element $e \in G$ is also in H .
- **Inverses:** For each $a \in H$, the inverse $a^{-1} \in H$.

4.2 Examples [3]

- In $(\mathbb{Z}, +)$, the set of even integers $2\mathbb{Z}$ is a subgroup.
- In (\mathbb{R}^*, \cdot) , the set of positive real numbers \mathbb{R}^+ is a subgroup.

5 Cosets

5.1 Definition

Given a subgroup H of G , a left coset of H in G is the set [1]:

$$gH = \{g \cdot h \mid h \in H\}, \quad g \in G.$$

Similarly, a right coset is defined as [1]:

$$Hg = \{h \cdot g \mid h \in H\}.$$

5.2 Properties

- gH or Hg is a subset of G , i.e., $gH \subseteq G$ and $Hg \subseteq G$.
- If $Hx = Hy$, then $Hx \cap Hy = \emptyset$ (cosets are either disjoint or identical).
- Cosets partition G .
- All cosets of H have the same cardinality as H .
- Cosets need not be subgroups of G [1].
- The number of distinct cosets is called the **index** of H in G , denoted $|G : H|$ [1].

5.3 Example: Cosets in \mathbb{Z}_6

Consider the group $\mathbb{Z}_6 = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$ under addition modulo 6. Let $H = \{0, 2, 4\}$ be a subgroup of \mathbb{Z}_6 .

The cosets of H are as follows:

$$H_0 = H_2 = H_4 = \{0, 2, 4\}, \quad H_1 = H_3 = H_5 = \{1, 3, 5\}.$$

5.3.1 Explanation

For any $x \in H$,

$$H_x = \{x + h \mid h \in H\} = H,$$

hence

$$H_0 = H_2 = H_4.$$

Similarly, for $x \notin H$,

$$H_x = \{x + h \mid h \in H\},$$

leading to the disjoint coset

$$H_1 = H_3 = H_5.$$

5.3.2 Partition

The group \mathbb{Z}_6 is partitioned into two disjoint cosets:

$$\mathbb{Z}_6 = H_0 \cup H_1 = \{0, 2, 4\} \cup \{1, 3, 5\}.$$

5.3.3 Index

The index of H in \mathbb{Z}_6 is:

$$|G : H| = 2.$$

This shows that \mathbb{Z}_6 is divided into two distinct cosets of H .

6 Normal Subgroups

6.1 Definition

A subgroup N of a group G is called a **normal subgroup** if it is invariant under conjugation, meaning [1]:

$$gN = Ng \text{ or equivalently, } gNg^{-1} = N \text{ for all } g \in G.$$

This implies that for any $n \in N$ and $g \in G$:

$$gng^{-1} \in N.$$

6.2 Notation for Normal Subgroups

A normal subgroup is denoted as:

$$N \triangleleft G,$$

indicating that N is a normal subgroup of G .

6.3 Examples

6.3.1 Trivial Subgroups

The trivial subgroup $\{e\}$ (containing only the identity element) and the entire group G are always normal subgroups of G .

6.3.2 Center of a Group

The **center** of a group G , denoted $Z(G)$, is defined as:

$$Z(G) = \{z \in G \mid zg = gz \text{ for all } g \in G\}.$$

The center $Z(G)$ is always a normal subgroup of G because the elements of $Z(G)$ commute with all elements of G [1].

6.4 Properties of Normal Subgroups

6.4.1 Conjugacy Invariance

A subgroup N of a group G is normal if and only if it is invariant under conjugation [1]:

$$gNg^{-1} = N \text{ for all } g \in G.$$

This means that for every $n \in N$ and $g \in G$, the conjugate element gng^{-1} is also in N .

6.4.2 Left and Right Cosets Coincide

A subgroup N is normal if and only if the left cosets and right cosets of N in G are the same:

$$gN = Ng \quad \text{for all } g \in G.$$

This ensures that the subgroup is symmetric under multiplication from both sides by any element in G [1].

6.4.3 Quotient Groups

If $N \triangleleft G$, the set of cosets G/N forms a group under the operation [2]:

$$(gN) \cdot (hN) = (gh)N, \quad \text{for all } g, h \in G.$$

This operation is well-defined because the cosets of a normal subgroup are stable under the group operation.

6.4.4 Kernel of a Homomorphism is Normal

If $\phi : G \rightarrow H$ is a group homomorphism, then the **kernel** of ϕ , denoted $\ker(\phi)$, is:

$$\ker(\phi) = \{g \in G \mid \phi(g) = e_H\},$$

where e_H is the identity element in H . The kernel is always a normal subgroup of G because it is invariant under conjugation [1].

6.4.5 Subgroups of Index 2 are Normal

If N is a subgroup of G with index 2 (i.e., $|G : N| = 2$), then N is automatically normal [1]. Since there are only two cosets, N and its complement, the group structure forces N to be invariant under conjugation.

6.4.6 Intersection of Normal Subgroups

The intersection of any collection of normal subgroups of G is also a normal subgroup of G [2]. This property allows the construction of new normal subgroups from existing ones by taking their intersection.

6.4.7 Relation with the Center

The center of a group,

$$Z(G) = \{z \in G \mid zg = gz \text{ for all } g \in G\},$$

is always a normal subgroup of G . The center contains elements that commute with every element of G , making it invariant under conjugation [1].

6.4.8 Normalizer Property

If $N \triangleleft G$, then:

$$N \subseteq N_G(N),$$

where $N_G(N)$, the **normalizer** of N , is defined as [2]:

$$N_G(N) = \{g \in G \mid gNg^{-1} = N\}.$$

The normalizer contains all elements of G that, when conjugated with N , leave N unchanged.

7 Examples of Normal Subgroups in Finite Groups

Let's break down the examples of normal subgroups in finite groups with explanations for each case.

7.1 Cyclic Group \mathbb{Z}_6 (Integers Modulo 6 under Addition)

Let $G = \mathbb{Z}_6$, the group of integers modulo 6 under addition:

$$G = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}.$$

A subgroup $H = \{0, 3\}$ is normal in G .

Reason: All subgroups of cyclic groups are normal because cyclic groups are abelian [1]. Since abelian groups are commutative, conjugation does not change elements. Thus, H is a normal subgroup of G .

7.2 Direct Product of Groups $G = \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_4$

Consider the direct product $G = \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_4$, which consists of ordered pairs of elements from \mathbb{Z}_2 and \mathbb{Z}_4 .

The elements of G are:

$$G = \{(0, 0), (0, 1), (0, 2), (0, 3), (1, 0), (1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3)\}.$$

Let $H = \{(0, 0)\}$ be a subgroup of G .

Reason: The subgroup $H = \{(0, 0)\}$ (the trivial subgroup) is normal in G , and this holds for all subgroups of direct products of abelian groups [1]. Since the direct product of abelian groups is itself abelian, all of its subgroups are normal.

7.3 General Linear Group $GL(2, \mathbb{Z}_3)$

Consider the group $G = GL(2, \mathbb{Z}_3)$, the group of invertible 2×2 matrices over the finite field \mathbb{Z}_3 (integers modulo 3).

This group consists of matrices whose determinant is nonzero modulo 3.

Subgroup H : The subgroup consisting of scalar matrices, where Let

$$A = \lambda I = \begin{pmatrix} \lambda & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda \end{pmatrix}, \quad \lambda \in \mathbb{Z}_3^* = \{1, 2\}.$$

Reason: The subgroup of scalar matrices is normal in $GL(2, \mathbb{Z}_3)$ because scalar matrices commute with all elements of $GL(2, \mathbb{Z}_3)$ [2]. This property ensures that the conjugate of any scalar matrix remains a scalar matrix, meaning the subgroup is normal.

8 Counting Normal Subgroups

Counting normal subgroups is a fundamental topic in group theory, focusing on identifying and quantifying the normal subgroups within a finite group G . This section outlines key concepts, examples, and methods for counting normal subgroups.

8.1 Conjugacy Class Analysis

- **Idea:** A normal subgroup is a union of conjugacy classes of G . Thus, the number and structure of conjugacy classes directly influence the count of normal subgroups [1].
- **Steps:**

1. Compute the conjugacy classes of G .
 2. Identify unions of conjugacy classes that satisfy subgroup properties.
- **Example:** In S_3 , the conjugacy classes are:

$$\{e\}, \quad \{(12), (13), (23)\}, \quad \{(123), (132)\}.$$

The normal subgroups are $\{e\}, S_3, A_3$, corresponding to unions of these classes [2].

8.2 Subgroup Lattice Examination

- **Idea:** The subgroup lattice (Hasse diagram) of G displays all subgroups. Identifying normal subgroups simplifies the counting process [1].
- **Steps:**
 1. Construct the lattice of all subgroups of G .
 2. Test normality: For each subgroup H , verify $gHg^{-1} = H$ for all $g \in G$.

8.3 Direct Enumeration

- **Idea:** In small groups, normality can be tested for each subgroup.
- **Steps:**
 1. List all subgroups of G .
 2. For each H , check $gHg^{-1} = H$ for all $g \in G$ [2].

8.4 Use of Quotient Groups

- **Idea:** Normal subgroups correspond to quotient groups G/N . By studying quotient group structures, normal subgroups can be inferred [3].
- **Steps:**
 1. Analyze all possible quotient groups G/N .
 2. Determine N from the structure of G/N .

8.5 Index-Based Methods

- **Idea:** Subgroups of certain indices (e.g., index 2) are automatically normal [1].
- **Steps:**
 1. List subgroups of G by their indices.
 2. Identify subgroups of index 2, 3, etc., and verify normality.
- **Example:** Any subgroup of index 2 in a group G is normal because there are only two cosets, which guarantees conjugacy invariance.

8.6 Sylow's Theorems

- **Idea:** In p -groups, Sylow's theorems provide information about the existence and number of subgroups of a given order, aiding in identifying normal subgroups [2].
- **Steps:**
 1. Determine Sylow p -subgroups.
 2. Check which Sylow p -subgroups are normal.

8.7 Group Extensions and Kernels

- **Idea:** The kernel of a homomorphism is always a normal subgroup. Studying group extensions helps in identifying such kernels [3].
- **Steps:**
 1. Define homomorphisms $\varphi : G \rightarrow H$.
 2. Compute $\ker(\varphi)$ and verify normality.

8.8 Counting in Abelian Groups

- **Idea:** In abelian groups, every subgroup is normal. The task reduces to counting subgroups [1].
- **Steps:**
 1. Decompose the abelian group G into cyclic components.
 2. Count the subgroups of each component and compute their product.
- **Example:** In \mathbb{Z}_{12} , there are 6 subgroups, all normal, corresponding to divisors of 12.

8.9 Normalizer Property

- **Idea:** A subgroup H is normal if $H = N_G(H)$, where $N_G(H)$ is the normalizer of H in G [3].
- **Steps:**
 1. Compute $N_G(H)$ for each subgroup H .
 2. Check if $H = N_G(H)$.
- **Example:** For a subgroup H of S_3 , the normalizer condition confirms whether H is normal.

9 Relation Between Normal Subgroups and Conjugacy Classes

Normal subgroups can be understood as unions of conjugacy classes, and this connection provides insight into both the structure of the group and the properties of its subgroups [1].

9.1 Normal Subgroups as Unions of Conjugacy Classes

A subgroup N of a group G is normal if and only if it is a union of conjugacy classes of G [1].

Explanation: The conjugacy class of an element $x \in G$ is:

$$Cl_G(x) = \{gxg^{-1} \mid g \in G\}.$$

For N to be normal, it must be invariant under conjugation, meaning that for every $n \in N$ and $g \in G$:

$$gng^{-1} \in N.$$

This ensures that N contains entire conjugacy classes [2].

9.2 Containment of the Identity Element

Every conjugacy class contains the identity element e , as:

$$geg^{-1} = e, \quad \text{for all } g \in G.$$

Thus, any normal subgroup N must include the identity element [1].

9.3 Properties Derived from the Relation

1. **Counting Normal Subgroups:** The number of normal subgroups of G depends on the distribution of its conjugacy classes. Fewer conjugacy classes often mean fewer possibilities for unions, leading to fewer normal subgroups [1].
2. **Conjugacy Class Size and Normality:** The size of a conjugacy class $Cl_G(x)$ is given by [2]:

$$Cl_G(x) = \frac{|G|}{|C_G(x)|},$$

where $C_G(x)$ is the centralizer of x in G . Elements in N must have conjugacy classes that divide $|N|$.

3. **Relation to Quotient Groups:** If N is a normal subgroup of G , then the quotient group G/N consists of cosets, which correspond to equivalence classes under conjugation [1].

9.4 Applications

1. **Determining Normal Subgroups:** By analyzing the conjugacy classes, we can quickly identify possible normal subgroups by combining classes [2].
2. **Counting Normal Subgroups:** For finite groups, the classification of conjugacy classes offers a systematic way to count the normal subgroups [1].

10 Normal Subgroups: Role of Group Actions, Automorphisms, and the Kernel of Homomorphisms

10.1 Using Group Actions to Identify Normal Subgroups

Group actions provide a powerful framework to study normal subgroups. A group G acting on a set X induces structures that reveal properties of G , including its normal subgroups [1].

10.1.1 Key Ideas

Action by Conjugation: The group G acts on itself by conjugation:

$$g \cdot x = gxg^{-1}, \quad \text{for all } g, x \in G.$$

The stabilizer of an element $x \in G$ under this action is its centralizer:

$$C_G(x) = \{g \in G : gx = xg\}.$$

The orbit of x under this action is its conjugacy class:

$$Cl_G(x) = \{gxg^{-1} \mid g \in G\} [2].$$

Normal Subgroups as Unions of Orbits: Normal subgroups $N \subseteq G$ are precisely the subsets of G that are unions of full conjugacy classes [2].

Orbit-Stabilizer Theorem: The size of a conjugacy class is given by:

$$Cl_G(x) = \frac{|G|}{|C_G(x)|}.$$

This provides a combinatorial tool to identify normal subgroups by examining conjugacy class sizes [1].

10.2 Role of Automorphisms

Automorphisms of a group G , which are isomorphisms from G to itself, play a significant role in identifying and characterizing normal subgroups [3].

10.2.1 Key Ideas

Inner Automorphisms: Each element $g \in G$ defines an inner automorphism:

$$\varphi_g(x) = gxg^{-1}.$$

The set of all inner automorphisms forms a group, $Inn(G)$, which is isomorphic to $G/Z(G)$, where $Z(G)$ is the center of G [3].

Normal Subgroups and Automorphism Groups: A subgroup $N \subseteq G$ is normal if and only if it is invariant under all inner automorphisms:

$$\varphi_g(N) = N \quad \text{for all } g \in G.$$

10.3 Role of the Kernel of Homomorphisms

The kernel of a homomorphism provides a direct method to identify normal subgroups [1].

10.3.1 Key Ideas

Definition: The kernel of a group homomorphism $\varphi : G \rightarrow H$ is:

$$\ker(\varphi) = \{g \in G \mid \varphi(g) = e_H\},$$

where e_H is the identity element in H [1].

Kernel is Always Normal: The kernel $\ker(\varphi)$ is a normal subgroup of G because:

$$\varphi(gxg^{-1}) = \varphi(g)\varphi(x)\varphi(g)^{-1} = e_H \quad \text{if } \varphi(x) = e_H.$$

This property ensures that kernels of homomorphisms always form normal subgroups [2].

11 Examples and Case Studies of Normal Subgroups in Small Finite Groups

Below is an analysis of normal subgroups in specific types of small finite groups, focusing on their structures, properties, and examples [1].

11.1 Cyclic Groups

Cyclic groups are among the simplest groups, generated by a single element.

11.1.1 Key Properties of Normal Subgroups in Cyclic Groups

- Every subgroup of a cyclic group is normal [1].
- If $G = \langle g \rangle$ is a cyclic group of order n , then every subgroup corresponds to a divisor of n [2].
- Subgroups of G are of the form $H_k = \langle g^{n/k} \rangle$, where k divides n .

Example: \mathbb{Z}_6 (Cyclic Group of Order 6)

$$\mathbb{Z}_6 = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5\} \quad (\text{under addition modulo 6})$$

Subgroups:

$$\langle 0 \rangle = \{0\} \quad (\text{trivial subgroup})$$

$$\langle 3 \rangle = \{0, 3\} \quad (\text{order 2})$$

$$\langle 2 \rangle = \{0, 2, 4\} \quad (\text{order 3})$$

$$\langle 1 \rangle = \mathbb{Z}_6 \quad (\text{entire group})$$

All these subgroups are normal because \mathbb{Z}_6 is abelian [1].

11.2 Symmetric Groups (e.g., S_3, S_4)

Symmetric groups consist of all permutations on a set of n elements, with order $n!$ [1].

11.2.1 Key Properties of Normal Subgroups in Symmetric Groups

- Symmetric groups S_n are not abelian, so not all subgroups are normal [2].
- For $n \geq 3$, the alternating group A_n (consisting of even permutations) is the largest proper normal subgroup of S_n .

Example: S_3 (Symmetric Group on 3 Elements)

$$S_3 = \{e, (12), (13), (23), (123), (132)\}, \quad \text{order 6}$$

Subgroups:

- Trivial subgroup $\{e\}$ (normal).
- Entire group S_3 (normal).
- Alternating group $A_3 = \{e, (123), (132)\}$ (normal) [1].
- Other subgroups, such as $\langle (12) \rangle = \{e, (12)\}$, are not normal.

11.3 Alternating Groups (e.g., A_4, A_5)

Alternating groups consist of all even permutations in S_n .

11.3.1 Key Properties

- For $n \geq 5$, alternating groups A_n are simple (have no proper nontrivial normal subgroups) [1].
- For smaller n , A_n may have nontrivial normal subgroups.

Example: A_4 (Alternating Group on 4 Elements)

$$A_4 = \{e, (123), (132), (234), (243), (341), (314), (124), (142), (12)(34), (13)(24), (14)(23)\}$$

Subgroups:

- $V_4 = \{e, (12)(34), (13)(24), (14)(23)\}$ (normal, known as the Klein four-group) [1].
- $\langle(123)\rangle = \{e, (123), (132)\}$ (not normal).
- The entire group A_4 is normal in S_4 .

11.4 Groups of Prime Order

Groups of prime order p are simple in structure.

11.4.1 Key Properties

- A group G of prime order p is cyclic, generated by a single element [2].
- It has exactly two subgroups:
 - The trivial subgroup $\{e\}$.
 - The entire group G .
- Both subgroups are normal because G is abelian [1].

Example: \mathbb{Z}_5 (Cyclic Group of Order 5)

$$\mathbb{Z}_5 = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\} \quad (\text{under addition modulo } 5)$$

Subgroups:

$$\langle 0 \rangle = \{0\}$$

$$\langle 1 \rangle = \mathbb{Z}_5$$

Both are normal [2].

11.5 Groups of Prime Power Order (e.g., p^n)

Groups of order p^n (for a prime p) have a more complex structure [1].

11.5.1 Key Properties

- Every group of order p^n has a nontrivial center $Z(G)$, which is a normal subgroup [2].
- Groups of order p^n are classified by their p -group structure and often have multiple normal subgroups.

12 Classification by Number of Normal Subgroups

Groups can be classified based on the number of normal subgroups they possess, offering insights into their structural properties and complexity [1, 2].

12.1 Groups with Exactly Two Normal Subgroups

Definition: These groups have only two normal subgroups:

- The trivial subgroup $\{e\}$, which contains only the identity element.
- The entire group G .

12.1.1 Key Properties

- Such groups are necessarily cyclic and of prime order p [3].
- By Lagrange's theorem, a group of prime order p has no proper non-trivial subgroups other than $\{e\}$ and G itself [4].
- These groups are simple in structure and always abelian.

12.1.2 Example: \mathbb{Z}_5 (Cyclic Group of Prime Order 5)

- **Group:** $\mathbb{Z}_5 = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ under addition modulo 5.
- **Subgroups:**
 - $\langle 0 \rangle = \{0\}$ (trivial subgroup).
 - $\langle 1 \rangle = \mathbb{Z}_5$ (entire group).
- Both subgroups are normal [1].

Note: Any group with exactly two normal subgroups must be isomorphic to a cyclic group of prime order [2].

12.2 Groups with More than Two Normal Subgroups

Definition: Groups with more than two normal subgroups have a more complex structure. The number of normal subgroups depends on factors like:

- The group's size.
- Whether the group is abelian or non-abelian.
- Its internal symmetries and subgroup relationships [3].

12.2.1 Key Properties

Abelian Groups

- All subgroups of an abelian group are normal.
- The number of normal subgroups corresponds to the divisors of the group's order [4].

12.2.2 Example: \mathbb{Z}_6 (Cyclic Group of Order 6)

- **Normal subgroups:**
 - $\{0\}$ (trivial subgroup).
 - $\langle 3 \rangle = \{0, 3\}$ (order 2).
 - $\langle 2 \rangle = \{0, 2, 4\}$ (order 3).
 - \mathbb{Z}_6 (entire group).
- Since \mathbb{Z}_6 is abelian, all of its subgroups are normal [1].

Non-Abelian Groups: Not all subgroups are normal.

12.2.3 Groups of Prime Power Order

These groups have rich normal subgroup structures due to Sylow's theorems [2].

Example: Groups of Order p^2 (e.g., $\mathbb{Z}_p \times \mathbb{Z}_p$)

- These groups typically have multiple normal subgroups, including the center and other characteristic subgroups [3].

12.3 Simple Groups

Definition: Simple groups are groups that have no non-trivial normal subgroups, meaning their only normal subgroups are:

- $\{e\}$ (trivial subgroup).
- G (entire group).

12.3.1 Key Properties

- Simple groups are the building blocks of group theory, similar to prime numbers in number theory [4].

12.3.2 Examples

- Groups of prime order (\mathbb{Z}_p).
- Certain finite non-abelian groups (e.g., A_5 , the alternating group of order 60).

12.3.3 Example: A_5 (Alternating Group of Degree 5)

- **Order:** 60.
- **Structure:**
 - A_5 is simple and has no proper normal subgroups.
 - The group is non-abelian and serves as a fundamental example of a finite simple group [1].

13 Role of Structure in Determining Normal Subgroups

The structure of a group plays a crucial role in determining its normal subgroups. Various group structures—abelian, non-abelian, and direct product groups—exhibit different behaviors regarding the existence and nature of their normal subgroups [1, 2].

13.1 Abelian Groups: All Subgroups Are Normal

Definition: A group G is abelian if $ab = ba$ for all $a, b \in G$. In such groups, every subgroup is normal because conjugation does not change the subgroup elements [1].

13.1.1 Key Properties

- **Conjugation Invariance:** For any subgroup $H \subseteq G$ and $g \in G$,

$$gHg^{-1} = H$$

since $g \cdot h \cdot g^{-1} = h$ for all $h \in H$.

- **Normal Subgroups = All Subgroups:** Every subgroup $H \subseteq G$ satisfies the normality condition $gHg^{-1} = H$.

13.1.2 Examples

- **Cyclic Groups:** \mathbb{Z}_n has all normal subgroups. Example: In \mathbb{Z}_6 , the subgroups $\{0\}$, $\{0, 3\}$, $\{0, 2, 4\}$, \mathbb{Z}_6 are all normal [2].
- **Direct Sum of Cyclic Groups:** $\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_3$. Example: The subgroup $\{(0, 0), (0, 3)\}$ is normal because the group is abelian [3].

13.2 Non-Abelian Groups: Only Certain Subgroups Are Normal

Definition: In non-abelian groups, the group operation is not commutative ($ab \neq ba$ for some $a, b \in G$). Not all subgroups are normal, as conjugation can map elements of a subgroup outside the subgroup [1].

13.2.1 Key Properties

- **Conjugacy and Normality:** A subgroup $N \subseteq G$ is normal if:

$$gNg^{-1} = N \quad \forall g \in G.$$

- **Non-Abelian Structures:** In many non-abelian groups, only specific subgroups, such as the center or kernels of homomorphisms, are normal [2].

13.2.2 Examples

- **Symmetric Group S_3 (Order: 6)**
 - $\{e\}$ (trivial subgroup) is normal.
 - $\langle(12)\rangle = \{e, (12)\}$ is not normal.
 - $\langle(123)\rangle = \{e, (123), (132)\}$ is normal.
 - The entire group S_3 is normal [3].
- **Dihedral Group D_4 (Order: 8)**
 - $\langle r \rangle = \{e, r, r^2, r^3\}$ is not normal.
 - $\langle r^2 \rangle = \{e, r^2\}$ is normal (center of D_4).
 - $\langle r, f \rangle$ (entire group) is normal [1].

14 Sylow Theorems and Normal Subgroups

The Sylow theorems provide important information about the existence and structure of subgroups of a finite group, particularly those whose orders are prime powers. These theorems help identify conditions under which certain subgroups are normal.

14.1 Connection Between Sylow p -Subgroups and Normal Subgroups

14.1.1 Definition

A Sylow p -subgroup of a finite group G is a maximal p -subgroup of G , meaning it is a subgroup of order p^n (where p^n is the largest power of p dividing $|G|$) and is not properly contained in any larger p -subgroup of G [?].

14.1.2 Key Properties of Sylow Theorems

- **Existence (First Sylow Theorem):** If p^n is the highest power of p dividing $|G|$, then G has at least one subgroup of order p^n [?].
- **Conjugacy (Second Sylow Theorem):** Any two Sylow p -subgroups of G are conjugate to each other, meaning if P and Q are Sylow p -subgroups, then there exists $g \in G$ such that:

$$gPg^{-1} = Q$$

This means all Sylow p -subgroups are structurally similar but not necessarily normal [?].

- **Number of Sylow p -Subgroups (Third Sylow Theorem):** Let n_p be the number of Sylow p -subgroups in G . Then:

$$n_p \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$$

and n_p divides $|G|$ [?].

14.2 Relation to Normal Subgroups

- If there is only one Sylow p -subgroup in G (i.e., $n_p = 1$), it must be normal.
- The uniqueness of a Sylow p -subgroup guarantees its normality since there is no other subgroup conjugate to it.
- **Uniqueness of Sylow Subgroups Leading to Normality:** If a Sylow p -subgroup P is unique, then for all $g \in G$,

$$gPg^{-1} = P.$$

Thus, $P \triangleleft G$ (i.e., P is normal in G) [?].

14.3 Examples

- **Example 1: S_3 and Sylow 2-Subgroups.**

$$|S_3| = 6 = 2^1 \times 3^1.$$

The Sylow 2-subgroups have order $2^1 = 2$. Possible Sylow 2-subgroups:

$$H_1 = \langle (12) \rangle, \quad H_2 = \langle (23) \rangle, \quad H_3 = \langle (13) \rangle.$$

Since $n_2 = 3 \neq 1$, no Sylow 2-subgroup is normal in S_3 [?].

- **Example 2: \mathbb{Z}_7 and Normal Sylow Subgroup.**

$$|\mathbb{Z}_7| = 7 = 7^1.$$

There is only one Sylow 7-subgroup: \mathbb{Z}_7 itself. Since it is unique, it is normal [?].

- **Example 3: D_8 and Normal Sylow Subgroup.**

$$|D_8| = 8 = 2^3.$$

The only Sylow 2-subgroup is $\langle r \rangle$, which is normal [?].

15 Normal Subgroups in Specific Group Classes

The structure and properties of normal subgroups vary significantly across different classes of groups. Below, we analyze normal subgroups in cyclic groups, p -groups, dihedral groups, and matrix groups.

15.1 Cyclic Groups

Definition. A cyclic group G is a group that can be generated by a single element, meaning:

$$G = \langle g \rangle = \{g^n \mid n \in \mathbb{Z}\}.$$

Cyclic groups can be finite (of order n) or infinite (\mathbb{Z}) [1].

Normal Subgroups in Cyclic Groups

- Every subgroup of a cyclic group is normal.
- If G is a finite cyclic group of order n , then its subgroups correspond to the divisors of n .
- If $G = \mathbb{Z}_n = \{0, 1, \dots, n-1\}$, then every subgroup is of the form $\langle d \rangle$, where d is a divisor of n [1].

Example. In \mathbb{Z}_{12} , the subgroups are:

$$\langle 1 \rangle, \langle 2 \rangle, \langle 3 \rangle, \langle 4 \rangle, \langle 6 \rangle, \langle 12 \rangle.$$

Each of these is normal.

Key Result. In cyclic groups, every subgroup is normal because cyclic groups are abelian [1].

15.2 p -Groups (Groups of Prime Power Order)

Definition. A p -group is a finite group whose order is a power of a prime p , i.e.,

$$|G| = p^n \quad \text{for some } n \geq 1.$$

Examples:

- \mathbb{Z}_p (cyclic of prime order).
- D_8 (dihedral group of order 8) [2].

Normal Subgroups in p -Groups

- Every nontrivial p -group has a nontrivial center, meaning it always has a nontrivial normal subgroup.
- **Frattini's Argument:** The intersection of all maximal subgroups of a p -group is always normal [2].

Example. $\mathbb{Z}_9 = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8\}$ (order 9). It has normal subgroups:

$$\langle 3 \rangle = \{0, 3, 6\}, \quad \langle 9 \rangle.$$

Key Result. Every p -group has a nontrivial normal subgroup, and its center is always nontrivial [2].

15.3 Dihedral Groups D_n (Symmetries of a Regular Polygon)

Definition. The dihedral group D_n consists of symmetries of a regular n -gon, including:

- n rotations r^k (where r is a $360^\circ/n$ rotation).
- n reflections sr^k .

It has the presentation:

$$D_n = \langle r, s \mid r^n = e, s^2 = e, srs = r^{-1} \rangle.$$

[3].

Normal Subgroups in Dihedral Groups

- For odd n , the only normal subgroups are the trivial subgroup and the whole group D_n .
- For even n , the rotation subgroup $\langle r \rangle$ is always normal [3].

Example: Normal Subgroups of D_4 (Dihedral Group of Order 8).

$$D_4 = \{e, r, r^2, r^3, s, sr, sr^2, sr^3\}.$$

- The rotation subgroup: $\langle r \rangle = \{e, r, r^2, r^3\}$ is normal.
- The center: $Z(D_4) = \{e, r^2\}$, which is also normal.
- Another normal subgroup: $\{e, r^2, s, sr^2\}$ [3].

Key Result:

- If n is odd: Only the trivial and whole group are normal.
- If n is even: The rotation subgroup $\langle r \rangle$ is normal [3].

15.4 Matrix Groups (Linear Groups Over a Field)

Definition. A matrix group is a group of invertible matrices under multiplication. Important examples:

- **General Linear Group** $GL(n, \mathbb{F})$: Invertible $n \times n$ matrices over a field \mathbb{F} .
- **Special Linear Group** $SL(n, \mathbb{F})$: Matrices with determinant 1.
- **Orthogonal Group** $O(n)$: Preserves dot product.
- **Symplectic Group** $Sp(2n, \mathbb{F})$: Preserves symplectic form [4].

Normal Subgroups in Matrix Groups

- The center of $GL(n, \mathbb{F})$ is the set of scalar matrices cI , where $c \neq 0$.
- $SL(n, \mathbb{F})$ is normal in $GL(n, \mathbb{F})$.
- The commutator subgroup, formed by commutators $ABA^{-1}B^{-1}$, is often normal [4].

Example: Normal Subgroups of $GL(2, \mathbb{R})$.

- The subgroup $SL(2, \mathbb{R})$ is normal in $GL(2, \mathbb{R})$.
- The set of scalar matrices $\{cI \mid c \in \mathbb{R}^\times\}$ forms a normal subgroup [4].

Key Result:

- Special linear groups $SL(n, \mathbb{F})$ are normal in $GL(n, \mathbb{F})$.
- The center of $GL(n, \mathbb{F})$ consists of scalar matrices [4].

15.5 Summary Table

Table 1: Normal Subgroups in Different Group Classes

Group Class	Key Normal Subgroups
Cyclic Groups	Every subgroup is normal
p -Groups	Always have a nontrivial normal subgroup
Dihedral Groups	Rotation subgroup is normal for even n
Matrix Groups	$SL(n, F)$ is normal in $GL(n, F)$

Conclusion

This research examined the number and nature of normal subgroups in finite groups, emphasizing their role in understanding group structure and classification. We discussed essential subgroup criteria and highlighted how group structure—whether abelian, non-abelian, simple, or a p -group—affects the existence and distribution of normal subgroups. Through detailed examples and classifications, we observed that certain groups, like cyclic groups of prime order, possess only two normal subgroups, while others, such as abelian or prime power order groups, often have many.

Key theoretical tools like Sylow theorems provided deeper insight into when subgroups are guaranteed to be normal, especially in finite groups. The study concludes that the number of normal subgroups is not arbitrary but is closely tied to the underlying algebraic structure of the group. This relationship not only aids in classifying finite groups but also contributes to a more refined understanding of their internal symmetries and subgroup dynamics.

References

- [1] J. B. Fraleigh, *A First Course in Abstract Algebra*, 7th ed. Pearson, 2002.
- [2] I. N. Herstein, *Topics in Algebra*, 2nd ed. Wiley, 1975.
- [3] S. Singh and Q. Zameeruddin, *Modern Algebra*, 8th ed. Vikas Publishing House, 2013.
- [4] J. A. Gallian, *Contemporary Abstract Algebra*, 8th ed. Cengage Learning, 2012.